

Capability Prediction of Machining Processes Based on Uncertainty Analysis

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Abstract—Prediction of machining process capability in the design stage plays a key role to reach the precision design and manufacturing of mechanical products. Inaccuracies in machining process lead to errors in position and orientation of machined features on the part, and strongly affect the process capability in the final quality of the product. In this paper, an efficient systematic approach is given to investigate the machining errors to predict the manufacturing errors of the parts and capability prediction of corresponding machining processes. A mathematical formulation of fixture locators modeling is presented to establish the relationship between the part errors and the related sources. Based on this method, the final machining errors of the part can be accurately estimated by relating them to the combined dimensional and geometric tolerances of the workpiece – fixture system. This method is developed for uncertainty analysis based on the Worst Case and statistical approaches. The application of the presented method is illustrated through presenting an example and the computational results are compared with the Monte Carlo simulation results.

Keywords—Process capability, machining error, dimensional and geometrical tolerances, uncertainty analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

DESIGN for manufacturing (DFM) is the basis for concurrent engineering (CE) to provide guidance to the design unit in improving of the product quality and to reduce manufacturing and assembly costs. Applying DFM in early stages of precision product design is necessary and significant. One aspect of the precision DFM is the error analysis of the manufacturing process. In manufacturing processes, especially the CNC machining, fixtures are the effective cause of the error propagation on features of the produced part. Fixture design is a complex problem that involves consideration of many operational requirements and has important connection with product quality and manufacturing cost. Fixtures are necessary elements of production processes as they are used to hold workpieces during most of manufacturing, inspection, and assembly operations [1]. Cecil et al. introduced a three-phase methodology for the fixture design activity has been developed [2]. The three phases include predesign analysis, functional analysis, and productivity improvement. The design of fixtures is an extremely complex process that requires the experiences of the human designers and for a given workpiece, multiple solutions may exist. Subramaniam et al. presented a multi-agent fixture design system which harnesses

the advantages of genetic algorithms and neural networks. The presented system attempts to capture the related domain knowledge and uses it to produce acceptable solutions efficiently [3].

When a workpiece is located on a fixture for machining or assembly operations, errors from several sources (e.g. setup errors and manufacturing errors such as machine vibration, tool-path errors, tool wear and tool deflection) affect the datum and target features on workpiece. Inaccuracies in workpiece location lead to errors in position and orientation of machined features on the workpiece, and thus, strongly affect the assemblability and the quality of the product. Therefore, a fixture must accurately locate a workpiece in a specific position and orientation with respect to a cutting tool or measuring device, or with respect to another component, such as in assembly processes (e.g. in a welding process).

Many researchers have worked on the effects of locating errors on the product quality with the aim of proposing more precise methods for evaluating these effects. Asada and By developed a kinematic model based on the full-rank Jacobian matrix of the constraint equations as a criterion that can be used to analyze the fixture layout and deterministic location scheme [4]. Rong and Bai considered the dependence of machining errors and operations in a tolerance analysis approach to estimate the machining errors in terms of linear and angular dimensions of a workpiece under a fixture design [5]. Choudhuri and DeMeter presented a model that relates datum establishment error to locator geometric variability [6]. The proposed model is limited to dimensional and profile tolerances in linear machined features that are bounded by planar workpiece surfaces. Rong et al. presented a locating error analysis approach for set-up planning and fixture design that included three techniques; a fixturing coordination system was defined to simulate the actual locating situation, a vectorial tolerance zone definition was explored and a locating error evaluation algorithm was developed with sensitivity analysis functions [7]. Zhang et al. presented an analytical set-up planning approach with three techniques; an extended graph to describe a feature and tolerance relationship graph and a datum and machining feature relationship graph, seven set-up planning principles to minimize machining error stack-up under a true positioning GD&T scheme; and tolerance decomposition models to partition a tolerance into interoperable machining errors [8]. Sangnui and Peters developed a mathematical model based on the Newton-Raphson technique to estimate the impact of component irregularities at the locating points on the location and orientation of a workpiece with cylindrical components [9].

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Wang presented a mathematic method to estimate locating error in the contact zones of fixture-workpieces in which there are the locator positional error and workpiece datum geometric error [10]. Kang et al. used the Jacobian matrix to formulate the relationship between locating point displacements and workpiece displacement. The proposed method takes into account the error caused by both locator position error and locator deformation [11]. Xiong et al. [12], [13] and Deng and Melkote [14] developed fixture models and optimized the locator layout as the deterministic location is only one of the locating schemes being able to hold the workpiece in the desired position. Qin et al. presented an analysis method that was able to characterize the effects of locating source errors based on the position and orientation of the workpiece [15]. With this model, the locating principle and a criterion of the robust optimal design were proposed to improve the locating quality of the fixture. Chairapat and Rujikietgumjorn developed a mathematical model to predict geometric variation of a resultant-machined surface when the tolerance of a datum feature is given [16]. Abe et al. presented a method for the machining error compensation [17]. The 3D surface data of the machined part is modified according to the machining error measured by CMM and a compensated NC program is generated from the modified 3D surface data for the machining error compensation. Armillotta et al. proposed a method to carry out kinematic and tolerance analysis through a common set of geometric parameters of the fixture configuration. Based on the presented method, in a poor designed fixture, the analysis provides suggestions to plan the needed corrections to the locating scheme [18]. Vishnupriyan et al. presented a method based on the genetic algorithm that can simultaneously optimize both workpiece elastic deformation and geometric errors of locators [19]. They developed a finite element model of the workpiece fixture system that obtained the elastic deformation of workpiece under machining loads. Zhu et al. presented a prediction model of a workpiece locating error caused by the setup error and geometric inaccuracy of locators for the fixtures with one locating surface and two locating pins [20]. Khodaygan introduced a mathematical method which can be used for eliminating the deviations of the located workpiece, the resultant geometric variations are expressed in the locator errors on the fixture [21], [22]. Based on the presented method, the displacement and rotation errors of the workpiece can be compensated by adjusting the length of locators.

In this paper, an efficient matrix-based approach for high accurate prediction of the capability of machining process is introduced. In order to reach to this aim, a mathematical formulation of machining fixture modeling is proposed to establish the relationship between the machining error and its sources. Unlike previous methods, the proposed approach can predict the machining errors of the part which has been involved with combination of geometrical and dimensional tolerances of the workpiece and the fixture. Using this method, the actual position of produced features on the located workpiece can be estimated accurately. The proposed method is a useful tool for designers, manufactures and inspectors for

precision design and manufacturing of mechanical parts and control of the final product accuracy under the production processes.

II. MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF LOCATING ERRORS IN THE FIXTURE LAYOUT

Now consider a workpiece located on a fixture as shown in Fig. 1. Let XYZ system be the global coordinate system and the i th locator be defined at "O" relative to it. Suppose r_{nlp} and r'_{nlp} be positions of the i th contact point between the workpiece and the i th locator in nominal and actual conditions, respectively. For mathematical modeling of locating errors in fixture layout, the following assumptions are made. First of all, according to the fundamental principles of fixture design, the located workpiece is in contact with all the six locators which are locating it. With assumption of limited small errors, this assumption seems rather logical. Secondly, the located workpiece is assumed to be rigid, i.e., they do not deform by locating process. Moreover, the contact point between the locator and the workpiece is assumed to be a point. The workpiece can slip on locators; this means that the primary or nominal contact points between the workpiece and the locators may be different. The nominal tangent plane to the workpiece with nominal geometry (without any tolerances) at the nominal position of the contact point can be described by;

$$\Gamma : n \cdot (r_p - r_{nlp}) = 0 \quad (1)$$

where n is the unit normal vector of the nominal tangent plane at the nominal contact point, ' $\cdot$ ' represents the dot product operator, r_p is the position vector of any point existing in the nominal tangent plane and r_{nlp} is the position vector of the nominal contact point between of the workpiece and the i th locator at nominal condition.

Fig. 1 The schematic of nominal and deviated tangent planes on a general workpiece

Let the locating errors due to manufacturing sources at i th locator position be δ where the contact point changed on located workpiece. The new tangent plane (Γ') at actual condition, the orientated unit normal vector (n') and changed contact point (r'_{nlp}) should be defined. In a similar way to equation of tangent plane at nominal condition, the equation of the new tangent plane at actual condition can be defined as

$$\mathbf{F}' : \mathbf{n}' \cdot (\mathbf{r}'_p - \mathbf{r}'_{nlp}) = 0 \quad (2)$$

Let $\mathbf{r}_o$ be the position vector of the center of the locator i (see Fig. 1). The radius of the locator i at nominal and actual conditions are r_l and $r_l + \delta r_l$ respectively. The locating error (δl) due to manufacturing sources as the manufacturing error of locator δr_l and the manufacturing error of workpiece δr_m in at i th locator position can be modeled as;

$$\delta l = \delta r_l + \delta r_m \quad (3)$$

Therefore, the position of contact point at actual condition ($\mathbf{r}'_{nlp}$) can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{r}'_{nlp} = \mathbf{r}_o + (l + \delta l) \mathbf{n}' \quad (4)$$

where the orientated unit normal vector ($\mathbf{n}'$) can be determined as

$$\mathbf{n}' = \mathbf{\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{n} \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{n}$ is the unit normal vector of the nominal tangent plane at the nominal contact point and $\mathbf{\Omega}$ is an orthogonal rotation matrix that can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{\Omega} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \beta \cos \gamma & \sin \alpha \sin \beta \cos \gamma - \cos \alpha \sin \gamma & \cos \alpha \sin \beta \cos \gamma + \sin \alpha \sin \gamma \\ \cos \beta \sin \gamma & \sin \alpha \sin \beta \sin \gamma + \cos \alpha \cos \gamma & \cos \alpha \sin \beta \sin \gamma - \sin \alpha \cos \gamma \\ -\sin \beta & \sin \alpha \cos \beta & \cos \alpha \cos \beta \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

α, β and γ are the rotation components of the located workpiece around x -, y -, and z - axes, respectively.

The $\mathbf{r}'_p$ is the position vector of any point existing in the actual nominal tangent plane that can be expressed based on the position of contact point at nominal condition ($\mathbf{r}_{nlp}$) as;

$$\mathbf{r}'_p = \mathbf{\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{r}_{nlp} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (7)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the pure small translation vector of the workpiece due to manufacturing errors.

III. MATRIX-BASED MODELING OF MACHINING ERRORS

The tangent plane equation at the actual situation (1) can be expressed as an implicit set of equations ($\Psi_i = 0$ where $i = 1, 2, \dots, 6$ or $\Psi = 0$) for all six locators. This equation system is appropriate to describe the small translations and the small rotations of the located workpiece on the fixture due to locating errors. The implicit equation system of the tangent plane at the nominal situation in general form can be expressed as;

$$\Psi(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{L}) = 0 \quad (8)$$

In a similar way, the implicit equation system of tangent planes at the actual situation in general form can be written as;

$$\Psi(\mathbf{X} + \delta \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{L} + \delta \mathbf{L}) = 0 \quad (9)$$

where $\delta \mathbf{X}$ and $\delta \mathbf{L}$ are the machining error and the locating error on the i th locator in the fixture layout, respectively.

Solving for the machining error in the implicit equation system of tangent planes at the actual situation would require a nonlinear equation solver. For linear analysis, the equation system can be linearized by the first order Taylor's series expansion. The linearized equation system can be written as;

$$\left(\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{X}} \right) \delta \mathbf{X} + \left(\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{L}} \right) \delta \mathbf{L} = 0 \quad (10)$$

This equation can be written in matrix form as;

$$[\mathbf{A}] \cdot [\Delta \mathbf{X}] + [\mathbf{B}] \cdot [\Delta \mathbf{L}] = 0 \quad (11)$$

To develop a general relationship between the machining error and the locating errors (that is called assembly function) in the explicit form, the equation system can be expressed as;

$$[\Delta \mathbf{X}] = [\mathbf{S}] \cdot [\Delta \mathbf{L}] \quad (12)$$

where $[\mathbf{S}]$ is the sensitivity matrix expressed as;

$$[\mathbf{S}] = -[\mathbf{A}]^{-1} \cdot [\mathbf{B}] \quad (13)$$

$[\mathbf{A}]$ and $[\mathbf{B}]$ matrices can be calculated as;

$$[\mathbf{A}_{ij}] = \left[\frac{\partial \Psi_i}{\partial x_j} \right] \quad i \text{ and } j = 1 \text{ to } 6 \quad (14)$$

where x_j for $j = 1$ to 6 are $x, y, z, \alpha, \beta, \gamma$, respectively.

$$[\mathbf{B}_{ij}] = \left[\frac{\partial \Psi_i}{\partial l_j} \right] \quad i \text{ and } j = 1 \text{ to } 6 \quad (15)$$

$$B_{ij} = \begin{cases} \frac{\partial \Psi_i}{\partial l_j} & i = j \\ 0 & i \neq j \end{cases}$$

$[\Delta \mathbf{L}]$ and $[\Delta \mathbf{X}]$ matrices are the locating error matrix and the machining error matrix, respectively.

By solving (12), the small translation vector $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ and the small rotation vector $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ of the located workpiece can be obtained based on the computed machining error matrix. Using these vectors, the actual position of any point on the located workpiece features related to its nominal position can be expressed as;

$$\mathbf{r}'_p = \mathbf{\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{r}_{np} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (16)$$

where $\mathbf{r}_{np}$ and $\mathbf{r}'_p$ are the nominal and the actual position vectors of a point on the located workpiece, respectively.

IV. ERROR ANALYSIS

In general form, the assembly function (12) can be written

as a mathematical relation between the dependent variables (the machining error matrix) and independent variables (the locating error matrix). There are two major types of error analysis based on the assembly response function; Worst Case and statistical methods. The Worst Case and statistical methods are two useful approaches in tolerance analysis of mechanical systems [23]-[26]. In this section, these two types of error analysis approaches are briefly reviewed.

A. Worst Case Approaches

The Worst Case (arithmetic) analysis simply supposes all effective variables in the assembly function are at maximum or minimum limits of related tolerances to simulate the worst possible combination [23]. It is, however, very rare in reality that all the components in a case study fall at their maximum or minimum tolerance levels at the same time. Therefore, this method does not present the real results in the error analysis.

For error analysis based on the worst case concept, the proposed method can be used in two strategies. The main difference between these two approaches is in using the signs of sensitivity and error values in the related computations. In the first approach, called the standard Worst Case analysis, only absolute values are used in the related computations. The proper relation for standard Worst Case analysis based on the proposed method can be written as [27];

$$\Delta x_i = \sum_{j=1}^n (|S_{ij}| \cdot |\Delta l_j|) \quad (17)$$

where S_{ij} is the value of sensitivity matrix, Δl_j and Δx_i are the values of the locating error and the machining error matrices, respectively.

In the second approach, called the direct method, the error values are used directly into the analytic assembly function and the computational results contain the sign effects of sensitivity and error values, therefore this method yields more precise results.

B. Statistical Approaches

There are several methods available for the statistical error analysis. Basically, the methods can be categorized into four classes [27], [28];

- Linear propagation method (Root sum square method)
- Non-linear propagation method (Extended Taylor series)
- Numerical integration method (Quadrature technique)
- Monte Carlo simulation method

The linear propagation method can be used if the assembly function is a linear. The root sum square method is based on the method of system moments. Assuming that the component feature dimensions are independent and normally distributed, proper relation for the statistical analysis based on the proposed method can be written as [29];

$$\Delta x_i = \left[\sum_{j=1}^n (S_{ij} \cdot \Delta l_j)^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (18)$$

where S_{ij} is the components of the sensitivity matrix, Δl_j and Δx_i are the components of the locating error and the machining error matrices, respectively.

If the analytic assembly function is non-linear, an extended Taylor series approximation can be used. In problems where the assembly function is not available in analytic form, the quadrature technique and Monte Carlo simulation can be utilized. Based on the quadrature technique, an approximation of the assembly function should be defined [28].

Monte Carlo simulation method is a computational tool for error analysis of mechanical assemblies, under very general situations. Monte Carlo simulation can be used in all situations in which the above three techniques can be used and can yield more precise estimates. The Monte Carlo simulation is an iterative method based on using a random number generator to simulate effects of variations due to errors on the effective variables in a system studied according to their expected behavior.

V. CAPABILITY OF MACHINING PROCESS

Process capability indices (PCIs) are extensively used to determine whether a process is capable of producing objects within customer specification limits or not. In general, a process capability index compares the natural variability of a process (see Fig. 2). In general form, the PCI can be defined as

$$PCI = \frac{\text{Allowable process spread}}{\text{Actual process spread}}$$

Fig. 2 Process capability index presents a relationship between the actual process performance and the specification limits

The capability ratio (CR) was used to describe the capability of processes when the average of the product characteristic was positioned at the nominal specification [30]. When the product average is at the nominal specification, both the lower and the upper specifications are an equal distance from the low end and high end of the product variation, respectively. The arithmetic for the CR is;

$$CR = \frac{\text{Total Specification}}{\text{Total Production Variation}}$$

A 1.33 capability ratio is the minimum required by most manufacturers and can easily be determined for the process. Total production variation for each control point (CP) on the produced feature can be geometrically defined as a spherical zone with radius r_{act} that called the total variation sphere

(TVS). The center position of TVS coincides with the nominal position of the corresponding control point (see Fig. 3). The TVS is locus of points that the actual position of CP may be probabilistically positioned in it. The r_{act} can be defined through two approaches;

i. Worst case concept;

$$r_{act} = |R_{act} - R_{nom}| \quad (19)$$

where R_{act} and R_{nom} are the actual and the nominal positions of CP with respect to the global coordinate system (GCS).

ii. Statistical concept;

$$r_{act} = k\sigma \quad (20)$$

where σ is the standard deviations of the actual positions of CP with respect to the GCS. k is an integer multiplier of σ based on k-Sigma concept. Similarly, the total specification can be defined as a spherical zone with radius r_{all} that called total specification sphere (TTS). The TVS and the TTS are concentric (Fig. 3). The r_{all} is the allowance error of the control points.

Fig. 3 Geometrical variations of the control point (CP) on the produced feature

The CR for the control point i on the produced feature can be defined as;

$$CR_i = \frac{r_{all_i}}{r_{act_i}} \quad (21)$$

where r_{all_i} and r_{act_i} are radii of TVS and TTS, respectively.

The capability ratio of the machining process can be estimated through the CRs that calculated for the control points of produced features;

$$CR = \min \{CR_1, CR_2, \dots, CR_n\} \quad (22)$$

VI. APPLICATION

In this section, a case study is presented to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed method. Consider an example where a workpiece is grasped by 6 locators of a fixture. The manufacturing processes create some geometric errors on features of the located workpiece within the previous stages of the production line. These geometric errors are presented as the dimensional and geometric tolerances on some features of the located workpiece as illustrated in Fig. 4.

The configuration of locators in the fixture layout and the related global coordinate system (GCS) are shown in Fig. 5.

Fig.4 The tolerances of workpiece due to the manufacturing processes within the previous stages of the production line

Positions of locators with respect to the global coordinate system and the related normal unit vectors at locators are reported in Table I. The locator and workpiece geometric errors to implement in proposed method are present in Table II.

Fig.5 The schematic of fixture layout and locators

TABLE I
 POSITION VECTORS OF THE LOCATORS AND THE RELATED NORMAL UNIT VECTORS IN THE GLOBAL COORDINATE SYSTEM

Locators	Position vectors	Normal unit vector	Δr_L	Δr_n
L1	(60, 5, 70)	(0, 1, 0)	-0.04	0.05
L2	(20, 5, 20)	(0, 1, 0)	-0.02	0.05
L3	(90, 5, 20)	(0, 1, 0)	-0.06	0.05
L4	(30, 45, 0)	(0, 0, 1)	0.01	0.00
L5	(80, 45, 0)	(0, 0, 1)	-0.02	0.00
L6	(110, 45, 40)	(-1, 0, 0)	-0.01	-0.01

TABLE II
 THE FIXTURE AND WORKPIECE GEOMETRIC ERRORS AT LOCATORS

Method	δx	δy	δz	$\delta \alpha$	$\delta \beta$	$\delta \gamma$
Direct method	-0.0268	0.0303	-0.0403	-0.00006	-0.00057	-0.00060
WC	0.0669	0.0509	0.0483	0.00057	0.00057	0.00060
RSS	0.0323	0.0243	0.0439	0.00034	0.00045	0.00045
Monte Carlo	μ -0.0027	-0.0015	-0.00452	0.00003	-0.00004	0.00001
	σ 0.0310	0.0273	0.0432	0.00037	0.00044	0.00046

The machining error matrix based on the proposed direct method can be computed by substituting the error values directly into the analytic assembly function (12). Also, the components of machining error matrix are computed using standard Worst Case, RSS and Monte Carlo simulation methods. The resulted components of machining error matrix

are reported in Table III. For Monte Carlo simulation, 200 random values are generated for components of the locating error matrix as input variables into the system of equations based on the normal (Gaussian) distribution type. Let μ and σ be the computed mean and standard deviation of workpiece error matrix components, respectively. On the other hand, the

computational results from Monte Carlo simulation method are dependent on the numbers of iterations and involve uncertainty. Therefore, it is useful to present the computed results of Monte Carlo simulation in interval form based on $\pm 3\sigma$ concept ($[\mu - 3\sigma, \mu + 3\sigma]$) are presented in Table III.

TABLE III
 THE RESULTED COMPONENTS OF MACHINING ERROR MATRIX

Method	δx	δy	δz	$\delta \alpha$	$\delta \beta$	$\delta \gamma$
Direct method	-0.02685	0.03029	-0.04028	-0.00006	-0.00057	-0.00060
WC	0.06686	0.05086	0.04828	0.00057	0.00057	0.00060
RSS	0.03235	0.02430	0.04390	0.00034	0.00045	0.00045
Monte Carlo	[-0.0958,0.0904]	[-0.0834,0.0804]	[-0.1342,0.1251]	[-0.0011,0.0011]	[-0.0014,0.0013]	[-0.0014,0.0014]

TABLE IV
 THE RESULTS BASED ON BOTH THE PROPOSED METHOD AND SIMULATIONS IN A CAD/CAM SYSTEM

Control points	Nominal position of control points in GCS	Actual position of control points in GCS		Deviation	
		Proposed method	Simulation results	Proposed method	Proposed method
CP ₁	(5.00,85.00,85.00)	(5.07,85.04,85.02)	(5.07,85.04,85.02)	0.083	0.083
CP ₂	(5.00,60.00,55.90)	(5.04,60.04,55.92)	(5.04,60.04,55.92)	0.060	0.060
CP ₃	(5.00,85.00,25.00)	(5.04,85.04,25.02)	(5.04,85.04,25.02)	0.060	0.060
CP ₄	(5.00,70.00,10.00)	(5.02,70.04,10.02)	(5.02,70.04,10.02)	0.049	0.049
CP ₅	(5.00,25.00,85.00)	(5.04,25.04,85.03)	(5.04,25.04,85.03)	0.064	0.064
CP ₆	(105.00,30.00,85.00)	(105.04,29.99,84.97)	(105.04,29.99,84.97)	0.051	0.051
CP ₇	(105.00,60.00,34.10)	(105.03,59.98,34.06)	(105.03,55.98,34.06)	0.054	0.054

According to Table III, the results based on the proposed direct method, unlike the results of standard Worst Case and root sum square methods, contain signs + or -, because in the direct method the error values and sensitivity coefficients are used directly into the analytic assembly function. Therefore, this method yields more precise results than the standard Worst Case method. By comparing the computed results based on the standard Worst Case and root sum square methods in Table III, it is observed that the components of the machining error matrix estimated by the statistical method are tighter than those estimated from standard Worst Case analysis. On the other hand, the computational intervals based on Monte Carlo simulation cover the results from other three methods.

For verification of the computed results, the workpiece and the related fixture with the specific geometric details are simulated in a CAD/CAM system. To consider the accuracy of the computed machining error matrix, the seven control points on the located workpiece are defined (see Fig. 6). Then, the related geometric workpiece and locator errors based on Worst Case concept are imposed on the CAD model, and the changed positions due to the errors and related deviations on the control points can be obtained. On the other hand, based on the proposed direct method, the actual position (r_{ap}) of any control point on the located workpiece features relative to its nominal position (r_{np}) can be computed by using (16) and the resulted machining error matrix of (12). Using the computed actual positions of any sample point with respect to their nominal positions, deviations of the control points can be estimated. The nominal and the resulted actual position of control points with respect to the global coordinate system and also the obtained deviations in position of control points through both the proposed direct method and the simulation in

the CAD/CAM system are reported in Table IV. According to Table IV, the proposed method presents the exact results that obtained through the simulation in the CAD/CAM system. Therefore, the proposed method accurately computes the located machining errors due to the geometric errors in the workpiece and the fixture.

Fig. 6 Position of control points on the located workpiece and the related global coordinate system (GCS)

The capability ratio of the machining process can be estimated through the CRs that calculated for the control points of produced features. Based on the computational results in Table IV and $r_{all} = 0.1 \text{ mm}$ as the allowance error of the control points, CRs are calculated for all control points (Fig. 7). According to Fig. 7, the control point 4 with the best quality has the maximum CR ($CR = 2.04$) and the control

point 1 with the worst quality has the minimum CR ($CR = 1.20$). Therefore, according to (22), the capability ratio of the machining process is equal with the minimum CR as 1.20. However, the $CR=1.2$ represents a good capability ration for the machining process. Therefore, computational results of CR s determine that the machining process is capable of producing objects within customer specification limits.

Using the proposed method helps designers, manufactures and inspectors to investigate and to control the final accuracy of products under manufacturing (especially the CNC machining) and the assembly processes. Based on the proposed method, an optimum design of the locating layout of fixtures can be resulted to reduce the geometric errors of the final product and to improve the quality of the fixture locating, including the reconfiguration of locators.

Fig. 7 Computational capability ratio of control points

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a mathematical method was introduced to predict machining process capability of the product. The presented method for modeling of machining errors in the located workpiece was developed according to principles of the fixture design. An efficient matrix-based formulation was used to analyze the machining errors due to the combined geometrical and dimensional tolerances of both the workpiece and the fixture. Unlike the previous methods, the presented approach can accurately predicted the actual position of produced features and the corresponding geometric deviations. Then, the CR of the machining process can be estimated through the minimum of CR s that calculated for the control points of produced features. The presented method can be used for machining error analysis and for feedback to the design unit for the part design improvement. The proposed approach can be easily automated for use within software. The presented error analysis method can be developed to reduce or to compensate the geometric errors of the product and to improve the quality of the fixture locating, including the reconfiguration of locators. The flexibility of the workpiece and the fixture has not been considered in the presented method, but this method can be improved to include the clamping effects in the fixture – workpiece system. A numerical example was presented to demonstrate the implementation of the proposed method and its results based on Worst Case analysis (the proposed direct and the standard

methods) and statistical analysis (the root sum square and Monte Carlo simulation methods) were discussed and the computational results were compared with the results of the CAD simulations. According to these comparisons, the proposed method presents the accurate and deterministic results that obtained through the simulation in the CAD/CAM system. The computational results of CR s determined that the machining process is capable of producing objects within customer specification limits.

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